

Project ‘The Third Way’
Prepositional Adverbials from Latin to Romance¹

**"Presenting aggregate fieldwork data with statistical measures
for the study of prepositional adverbials in Romance: a template.
Tables to be filled in by the fieldworkers"**

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Abstract

Complex adverbials built with the pattern ‘Preposition + Adjective’, like Italian *sul serio* ‘seriously’ or Spanish *sobre seguro* ‘without risk’, display pan-Romantic consistency. Nevertheless, they have been largely neglected by research in grammar. The *Third Way* project on ‘Prepositional Adverbials from Latin to Romance’ intends to fill this gap. It subjects a selection of prepositional adverbials in eight Romance dialects to a historico-varietal analysis to trace their continuity and variational trajectory, from Latin up to present-day usage. This project deliverable presents a template for the statistical processing of contemporary data drawn from the targeted dialects, more exactly the tables used by the fieldworkers. It completes two forthcoming journal articles presenting the method developed for statistical data processing and for the realisation of the enquiries, a test calculator developed for the statistical interpretation of linguistic data (Roy 2021) as well as a questionnaire model (Wissner et al. 2020, 10.5281/zenodo.3922232).

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Introduction

Complex adverbials built with the pattern ‘Preposition + Adjective’, like Catalan *d’ordinari* ‘ordinarily’, French *pour de vrai* ‘really’, Italian *sul serio* ‘seriously’, Portuguese *em especial* ‘especially’, Romanian *cu drept* ‘for sur’ or Spanish *sobre seguro* ‘without risk’ display pan-Romantic consistency (Hummel 2019a/b). Nevertheless, they have been largely neglected by research in grammar (Hummel *et al.* 2019). The *Third Way* project on ‘Prepositional Adverbials from Latin to Romance’, funded by the Austrian Research Fund nr. P 30751-G30 (2018-2021), intends to fill this gap. It subjects a selection of prepositional adverbials to a historico-varietal analysis in a comparative Pan-Romance approach to trace their continuity and variational trajectory, from Latin up to present-day usage. This paper presents a template for the statistical processing of contemporary data drawn from eight Romance dialects, more exactly the tables used by the fieldworkers.

Fieldworkers enter data that has been retrieved by the means of qualitative semi-directive enquiries realised with at least 20 speakers in each of the targeted Romance dialects (Wissner in print). The enquiries mainly aimed at finding out whether a list of prepositional adverbials, of which 25 are tested in all dialects, are known in these dialects, and if so, how they are used. We are particularly interested in their frequency and chronological, situational or social restrictions; due to the small of number of informants, these parameters are mainly identified on the basis of the speakers’ perception; these can (or not) correspond to effective usage in their group; generational differences are also examined considering the speakers’ age.

More exactly, the enquiries aim at extracting comparable data for the different areas on:

- the existence, in synchrony, of a series of prepositional adverbials or, failing that, the existence of variants, synonyms and associated forms,
- the prepositional adverbials’ syntagmatic and paradigmatic features,
- their variational features including chronological differences, frequency, formality and orality,
- their vitality, that is: their vigour of usage in a group of speakers.

The method underlying the template which is presented here has been tested with forms chosen randomly from data retrieved by team members Stefan Koch and Cesarina Vecchia in Campania, in the South of Italy (Montella).

This document completes

- 1) A questionnaire model: a guide, a questionnaire template (including questions, numbered A.1 to C.2) and a series of worksheets (Wissner/Porcel Bueno/Koch/Hummel 2020)
- 2) A test calculator, developed for the statistical interpretation of linguistic data retrieved in the field, Roy’s calculator (2021)
- 3) A journal article presenting the method developed for the realisation of enquiries in the field (Wissner in print)
- 4) A journal article presenting the method developed for statistical data processing (Wissner/Roy, forthcoming).

1. Correlating raw data with the speakers’ metadata for two cells of subgroups

1.1. Raw data for individual speakers in the test population

I Meta data with values	Gender m / f*	Age	A.1** Recogn- ition (0-10)	A.2 Local recogni- tion (0-10)	B.1 Fre- quency (1-7.5- 10)	B.2 Age- distribu- -tion (1-5.5- 10)	B.3 Infor- mal- ity (1- 5.5- 10)	B.4 Ora- lity (1-5.5- 10)	C.1 Varia- tion 1 (0-10)	C.2 Varia- tion 2 (0-10)	A.1	A.2	B.1	B.2	B.3	B.4	C1	C2	A.1	A.2	B.1	B.2	B.3	B.4	C1	C2	
Scale Item / Speak- er nr.	nr	→	Item 1: ...								2: ...								3: ...								
1																											
2																											
3																											
4																											
5																											
6																											
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24																											
25																											

* Choice of cells and sub-cells as argued in Wissner (in print); also see below.

** Questions numbered according to Wissner *et al.* 2020.

Table 1: Raw data for each individual speaker and each question, juxtaposed to synthesised metadata (items 1 to 3) [to be reproduced for the following items if used]

2. Analysing fieldwork data to identify the prepositional adverbials' usage

Instructions for fieldworkers:

- 1) Please report all raw data from your first table here.
- 2) Then calculate the values for each:
 - a. Percentages;
 - b. Median values with uncertainties (measured with Roy 2021);
 - c. *P*-values (calculated using Lowry 2001-2020).
- 3) You may want to highlight *P*-values which are significant (< 0.05) in green (cf. Wissner/Roy forthcoming p. 8).
- 4) Tables below are given for the first items (at least two). Simply copy them for further items.
- 5) 4 age-groups are only filled in
 - if in your dialect, there are at least 5 speakers per age sub-group 18-29, 30-45, 46-65, 66+;
 - for items that are recognised by at least 18 speakers (as argued in Wissner/Roy forthcoming).
- 6) In the tables in section 2, uncertainties according to the 83% confidence interval (CI) are only necessary for 2 sub-groups (see models below); indeed, since they aim at visualising data, 83% CI-results for four sub-cells (i.e., 4 age-groups) are only needed for combined values in section 3 (vitality), as these are correlated with four age groups (Wissner/Roy forthcoming p. 16 for these confidence intervals).
Currently, this model provides you with 4 distinct mobility criteria (geolinguistic mobility vs

2.1. Recognition: Do speakers know the tested prepositional adverbials? (A.1 – A.2 – A.3)

Question A.1: Have you already heard this expression?

Possible answers: Yes/No/Not sure.

Question A.2: Have you also heard this expression here in the area?

Possible answers: Yes/No/Not sure.

Significance thresholds (as argued in Wissner/Roy forthcoming; also see below):

“Unknown” (under 2, according to the number of people answering)

|| “Little known” (up to 3.7)

|| “Well-known” (3.8-7.2)

|| “Very well-known” (7.3-10)

A.1-A.2 Recognition	A.1	A.1	A.1	A.1	A.1	A.2	A.2	A.2	A.2	A.2
<i>Categories exclusive</i> <i>Answers in absolute numbers and %</i>	Recognition 0: Not sure (reported to 0)	0: No	10: Yes	I.a Value on a scale of 0 to 10	I.a Signifi- cance (<i>p</i>)	Recognition locally 0: NS	0: No	10: Yes	II.a Value (scale 0-10)	II.b Group- dependency (<i>p</i>)
Language [Place] <i>Item 1:</i> ...	..	.. (...%)	.. (...%)	... +... / -... [83 % CI: +... / -...]		..	.. (...%)	.. (...%)	... +... / -... [83 % CI: +... / -...]	
Female speakers	...	...	...	... +... / -... [83 % CI: +... / -...]	<i>p</i> = 0...	...	...	...	... +... / -... [83 % CI: +... / -...]	<i>p</i> = 0...
Male speakers	...	...	...	... +... / -... [83 % CI: +... / -...]		...	...	...	... +... / -... [83 % CI: +... / -...]	
Younger speakers	...	...	...	... +... / -... [83 % CI: +... / -...]	<i>p</i> = 0...	...	...	...	... +... / -... [83 % CI: +... / -...]	<i>p</i> = 0...
Elder speakers	...	...	...	... +... / -... [83 % CI: +... / -...]		...	...	...	... +... / -... [83 % CI: +... / -...]	
Speakers aged 18 to 29	...	...	...	... +... / -...	<i>p</i> = ...	...	...	...	... +... / -...	<i>p</i> = ...
Speakers aged 30-45	...	...	...	... +... / -...		...	...	...	... +... / -...	
Speakers aged 46 to 65	...	...	...	... +... / -...	<i>p</i> = ...	...	...	...	... +... / -...	<i>p</i> = ...
Speakers aged 66 or more	...	...	...	... +... / -...		...	...	...	... +... / -...	
Language [Place] <i>Item 2:</i> ...	...	.. (...%)	.. (...%)	... +... / -... [83 % CI: +... / -...]		...	.. (...%)	.. (...%)	... +... / -... [83 % CI: +... / -...]	
Female speakers	...	...	...	... +... / -... [83 % CI: +... / -...]	<i>p</i> = 0...	...	...	...	... +... / -... [83 % CI: +... / -...]	<i>p</i> = 0...
Male speakers	...	...	...	... +... / -... [83 % CI: +... / -...]		...	...	...	... +... / -... [83 % CI: +... / -...]	
Younger speakers	...	...	...	... +... / -... [83 % CI: +... / -...]	<i>p</i> = 0...	...	...	...	... +... / -... [83 % CI: +... / -...]	<i>p</i> = 0...
Elder speakers	...	...	...	... +... / -... [83 % CI: +... / -...]		...	...	...	... +... / -... [83 % CI: +... / -...]	
Speakers aged 18 to 29	...	...	...	... +... / -...	<i>p</i> = ...	...	...	...	... +... / -...	<i>p</i> = ...
...	...	...	...	... +... / -...		...	...	...	... +... / -...	

In the questionnaire’s bloc A, speakers are also asked if they can think of any examples:

Question A.3: Could you give an example?

Free answer.

A.3 Examples (raw data)	Age (clear < 46, dark > 45)	Gen -der f/m	Examples
Language [Place] <i>Item 1: ...</i>			
Speaker code			...
Language [Place] <i>Item 2: ...</i>			
Speaker code			...
Language [Place] <i>Item 3: ...</i>			
Speaker code			...

Table 2.1 bis: Analysis: A.3. Examples of the adverbials’ usage

2.2. Variational features: Which situations/speakers are prepositional adverbials attributed to?

2.2.1. Perceptive frequency (B.1)

Question B.1: Do you have the impression that this expression is frequent?
 Possible answers: Very frequent – frequent – not frequent – do not know.
 Thresholds: “Not frequent” (1-6.9) || “Frequent” (7.0-9.2) || “Very frequent”(9.3-10)

B.1 Frequency Categories exclusive Answers (raw data) in absolute numbers and % (1 line per item)	NS = not sure (reported to 1)	1. Not frequent (add NS)	7.5 Frequent	10. Very frequent	II.a Value (1-10)	III. Significance of group- dependency (probability)
Language [Place] Item 1: ...	...	... (...%)	... (...%)	... (...%)	... +... / -... [83% CI: +... / -...]	
Female speakers	...	...	...	...	... +... / -... [83% CI: +... / -...]	$p =$...
Male speakers	...	...	...	...	... +... / -... [83% CI: +... / -...]	
Younger speakers	...	...	...	...	... +... / -... [83% CI: +... / -...]	$p =$...
Elder speakers	...	...	...	...	... +... / -... [83% CI: +... / -...]	
Speakers aged 18 to 29	...	...	...	...	... +... / -...	$p =$...
Speakers aged 30-45	...	...	...	...	... +... / -...	
Speakers aged 46 to 65	...	...	...	...	... +... / -...	$p =$...
Speakers aged 66 or more	...	...	...	...	... +... / -...	
Language [Place] Item 2: ...	...	... (...%)	... (...%)	... (...%)	... +... / -... [83% CI: +... / -...]	
Female speakers	...	...	...	...	... +... / -... [83% CI: +... / -...]	$p =$...
Male speakers	...	...	...	...	... +... / -... [83% CI: +... / -...]	
Younger speakers	...	...	...	...	... +... / -... [83% CI: +... / -...]	$p =$...
Elder speakers	...	...	...	...	... +... / -... [83% CI: +... / -...]	
Speakers aged 18 to 29	...	...	...	...	... +... / -...	$p =$...
Speakers aged 30-45	...	...	...	...	... +... / -...	
Speakers aged 46 to 65	...	...	...	...	... +... / -...	$p =$...
Speakers aged 66 or more	...	...	...	...	... +... / -...	

Table 2.2.1: Analysis: B.1. The adverbials’ perceptive frequency

2.2.2. Who uses the prepositional adverbials? Perceptive age-distribution (B.2)

Question B.2: Who generally uses the expression? [If there is no answer, the interviewer can help with suggestions, e.g., youngsters, the elderly, people from elsewhere...?] – Free answer.

Significance thresholds:

“Younger people” (1-3.7) || “Everyone / No-one in particular” (3.8-7.2) || “Elderly people” (7.3-10)

B.2 WHO (Speakers’ perceptive age) <i>Groups of categories: exclusive; Multiple answers in absolute numbers</i>	0. Not sure	1. Younger people (...%)	5.5 Everyone / No one in particular (...%)	10. Elderly people (...%)	II.a Age-attribution (value) (scale 1-10)	II.b Signifi- cance of group depend- ency
Language [Place] Item 1: ...	...	...	...	...	... +... / -... [83% CI: +... / -...]	
Female speakers	...	...	...	...	... +... / -... [83% CI: +... / -...]	p = ...
Male speakers	...	...	...	...	... +... / -... [83% CI: +... / -...]	
Younger speakers	...	...	...	...	... +... / -... [83% CI: +... / -...]	p = ...
Elder speakers	...	...	...	...	... +... / -... [83% CI: +... / -...]	
Speakers aged 18 to 29	...	...	...	...	... +... / -...	p = ...
Speakers aged 30-45	...	...	...	...	... +... / -...	
Speakers aged 46 to 65	...	...	...	...	... +... / -...	p = ...
Speakers aged 66 or more	...	...	...	...	... +... / -...	
Language [Place] Item 2: ...	...	...	...	...	... +... / -... [83% CI: +... / -...]	
Female speakers	...	...	...	...	... +... / -... [83% CI: +... / -...]	p = ...
Male speakers	...	...	...	...	... +... / -... [83% CI: +... / -...]	
Younger speakers	...	...	...	...	... +... / -... [83% CI: +... / -...]	p = ...
Elder speakers	...	...	...	...	... +... / -... [83% CI: +... / -...]	
Speakers aged 18 to 29	...	...	...	...	... +... / -...	p = ...
Speakers aged 30-45	...	...	...	...	... +... / -...	
Speakers aged 46 to 65	...	...	...	...	... +... / -...	p = ...
Speakers aged 66 or more	...	...	...	...	... +... / -...	
Language [Place] Item 3: ...	...	...	...	...	... +... / -... [83% CI: +... / -...]	
Female speakers	...	...	...	...	... +... / -... [83% CI: +... / -...]	p = ...
Male speakers	...	...	...	...	... +... / -... [83% CI: +... / -...]	
Younger speakers	...	...	...	...	... +... / -... [83% CI: +... / -...]	p = ...
Elder speakers	...	...	...	...	... +... / -... [83% CI: +... / -...]	
Speakers aged 18 to 29	...	...	...	...	... +... / -...	p = ...
Speakers aged 30-45	...	...	...	...	... +... / -...	
Speakers aged 46 to 65	...	...	...	...	... +... / -...	p = ...
Speakers aged 66 or more	...	...	...	...	... +... / -...	

Table 2.2.2: Analysis: B.2. The adverbials’ perceptive age-distribution: Who uses them?

2.2.3. Who uses the prepositional adverbials? Perceptive social attribution (B.2b)

Significance thresholds (see above): “Educated people” (1-3.7)
 || “Everyone / No-one in particular” (3.8-7.2) || “The less educated” (7.3-10)

B.2 WHO (Speakers’ perceptive social identity) <i>Groups of categories: exclusive; Multiple answers in absolute numbers</i>	0. Not sure	1. Educated people	5.5 Everyone / No one in particular	10. Less educated people	II.a Social attribution (value) (scale 1-10)	II.b Significance of group dependency
Language [Place] Item 1: ...	...	... (...%)	Report from above	... (...%)	... +... / -... [83% CI: +... / -...]	
Female speakers	...	...	...	...	... +... / -... [83% CI: +... / -...]	$p = \dots$
Male speakers	...	...	...	...	... +... / -... [83% CI: +... / -...]	
Younger speakers	...	...	<i>Idem</i>	...	... +... / -... [83% CI: +... / -...]	$p = \dots$
Elder speakers	...	...	<i>Idem</i>	...	... +... / -... [83% CI: +... / -...]	
Speakers aged 18 to 29	...	...	...	...	... +... / -...	$p = \dots$
Speakers aged 30-45	...	...	...	...	... +... / -...	
Speakers aged 46 to 65	...	...	...	...	... +... / -...	$p = \dots$
Speakers aged 66 or more	...	...	...	...	... +... / -...	
Language [Place] Item 2: ...	...	... (...%)	<i>Idem</i>	... (...%)	... +... / -... [83% CI: +... / -...]	
Female speakers	...	...	...	...	... +... / -... [83% CI: +... / -...]	$p = \dots$
Male speakers	...	...	...	...	... +... / -... [83% CI: +... / -...]	
Younger speakers	...	...	<i>Idem</i>	...	... +... / -... [83% CI: +... / -...]	$p = \dots$
Elder speakers	...	...	<i>Idem</i>	...	... +... / -... [83% CI: +... / -...]	
Speakers aged 18 to 29	...	...	...	...	... +... / -...	$p = \dots$
Speakers aged 30-45	...	...	...	...	... +... / -...	
Speakers aged 46 to 65	...	...	...	...	... +... / -...	$p = \dots$
Speakers aged 66 or more	...	...	...	...	... +... / -...	
Language [Place] Item 3: ...	...	... (...%)	<i>Idem</i>	... (...%)	... +... / -... [83% CI: +... / -...]	
Female speakers	...	...	...	...	... +... / -... [83% CI: +... / -...]	$p = \dots$
Male speakers	...	...	...	...	... +... / -... [83% CI: +... / -...]	
Younger speakers	...	...	<i>Idem</i>	...	... +... / -... [83% CI: +... / -...]	$p = \dots$
Elder speakers	...	...	<i>Idem</i>	...	... +... / -... [83% CI: +... / -...]	
Speakers aged 18 to 29	...	...	...	...	... +... / -...	$p = \dots$
Speakers aged 30-45	...	...	...	...	... +... / -...	
Speakers aged 46 to 65	...	...	...	...	... +... / -...	$p = \dots$
Speakers aged 66 or more	...	...	...	...	... +... / -...	
Language [Place] Item 4: ...	...	... (...%)	<i>Idem</i>	... (...%)	... +... / -... [83% CI: +... / -...]	
Female speakers	...	...	...	...	... +... / -... [83% CI: +... / -...]	$p = \dots$
Male speakers	...	...	...	...	... +... / -... [83% CI: +... / -...]	
Younger speakers	...	...	<i>Idem</i>	...	... +... / -... [83% CI: +... / -...]	$p = \dots$
Elder speakers	...	...	<i>Idem</i>	...	... +... / -... [83% CI: +... / -...]	
Speakers aged 18 to 29	...	...	...	...	... +... / -...	$p = \dots$
Speakers aged 30-45	...	...	...	...	... +... / -...	
Speakers aged 46 to 65	...	...	...	...	... +... / -...	$p = \dots$
Speakers aged 66 or more	...	...	...	...	... +... / -...	

Table 2.2.3: Analysis: B.2. The adverbials’ perceptive social attribution: Who uses them?

B.2b WHO (Other social attributions) <i>Groups of categories: exclusive; Multiple answers in absolute numbers</i>	0. Not sure	1. If applicable add category	5.5 Everyone (if applicable)	10. If applicable add category	II.a Other social attributions (value) (scale 1-10)	II.b Signifi- cance of group depend- ency
Language [Place] Item 1: ...	...	... (...%)	<i>Report from above</i>	... (...%)	... +... / -... [83% CI: +... / -...]	
Female speakers	...	...	...	...	... +... / -... [83% CI: +... / -...]	<i>p</i> = ...
Male speakers	...	...	...	...	... +... / -... [83% CI: +... / -...]	
Younger speakers	...	...	<i>Idem</i>	...	... +... / -... [83% CI: +... / -...]	<i>p</i> = ...
Elder speakers	...	...	<i>Idem</i>	...	... +... / -... [83% CI: +... / -...]	
Speakers aged 18 to 29	...	...	...	...	... +... / -...	<i>p</i> = ...
Speakers aged 30-45	...	...	...	...	... +... / -...	
Speakers aged 46 to 65	...	...	...	...	... +... / -...	<i>p</i> = ...
Speakers aged 66 or more	...	...	...	...	... +... / -...	
Language [Place] Item 2: ...	...	... (...%)	<i>Idem</i>	... (...%)	... +... / -... [83% CI: +... / -...]	
Female speakers	...	...	...	...	... +... / -... [83% CI: +... / -...]	<i>p</i> = ...
Male speakers	...	...	...	...	... +... / -... [83% CI: +... / -...]	
Younger speakers	...	...	<i>Idem</i>	...	... +... / -... [83% CI: +... / -...]	<i>p</i> = ...
Elder speakers	...	...	<i>Idem</i>	...	... +... / -... [83% CI: +... / -...]	
Speakers aged 18 to 29	...	...	...	...	... +... / -...	<i>p</i> = ...
Speakers aged 30-45	...	...	...	...	... +... / -...	
Speakers aged 46 to 65	...	...	...	...	... +... / -...	<i>p</i> = ...
Speakers aged 66 or more	...	...	...	...	... +... / -...	
Language [Place] Item 2: ...	...	... (...%)	<i>Idem</i>	... (...%)	... +... / -... [83% CI: +... / -...]	
Female speakers	...	...	...	...	... +... / -... [83% CI: +... / -...]	<i>p</i> = ...
Male speakers	...	...	...	...	... +... / -... [83% CI: +... / -...]	
Younger speakers	...	...	<i>Idem</i>	...	... +... / -... [83% CI: +... / -...]	<i>p</i> = ...
Elder speakers	...	...	<i>Idem</i>	...	... +... / -... [83% CI: +... / -...]	
Speakers aged 18 to 29	...	...	...	...	... +... / -...	<i>p</i> = ...
Speakers aged 30-45	...	...	...	...	... +... / -...	
Speakers aged 46 to 65	...	...	...	...	... +... / -...	<i>p</i> = ...
Speakers aged 66 or more	...	...	...	...	... +... / -...	
Language [Place] Item 4: ...	...	... (...%)	<i>Idem</i>	... (...%)	... +... / -... [83% CI: +... / -...]	
Female speakers	...	...	...	...	... +... / -... [83% CI: +... / -...]	<i>p</i> = ...
Male speakers	...	...	...	...	... +... / -... [83% CI: +... / -...]	
Younger speakers	...	...	<i>Idem</i>	...	... +... / -... [83% CI: +... / -...]	<i>p</i> = ...
Elder speakers	...	...	<i>Idem</i>	...	... +... / -... [83% CI: +... / -...]	
Speakers aged 18 to 29	...	...	...	...	... +... / -...	<i>p</i> = ...
Speakers aged 30-45	...	...	...	...	... +... / -...	
Speakers aged 46 to 65	...	...	...	...	... +... / -...	<i>p</i> = ...
Speakers aged 66 or more	...	...	...	...	... +... / -...	

Table 2.2.3b: Analysis: B.2b. The adverbials' other perceptive social attributions: Who else uses them?

2.2.4. When are the prepositional adverbials used? Situational attribution (B.3)

Question B.3: When do people tend to use this expression (e.g., with friends, on TV, ...)?

Free answer.

Thresholds: “Formal” (1-3.7) || “No situation in particular” (3.8-7.2) || “Informal” (7.3-10)

B.3.a WHEN (situational) On the basis of speaker judgment <i>Categorised under 1 and 10 are exclusive;</i> <i>Answers in absolute numbers</i>	0. Not sure (reported to 5.5)	1. Formal	5.5 No situation in particular / Both (add NS)	10. In- formal	II.a Other social attributions (value) (scale 1-10)	II.b Signifi- cance of group depend- ency
Language [Place] Item 1: ...	...	... (...%)	... (...%)	... (...%)	... +... / -... [83% CI: +... / -...]	
Female speakers	...	...	...	...	... +... / -... [83% CI: +... / -...]	<i>p</i> = ...
Male speakers	...	...	...	...	... +... / -... [83% CI: +... / -...]	
Younger speakers	...	...	...	...	... +... / -... [83% CI: +... / -...]	<i>p</i> = ...
Elder speakers	...	...	...	...	... +... / -... [83% CI: +... / -...]	
Speakers aged 18 to 29	...	...	...	...	... +... / -...	<i>p</i> = ...
Speakers aged 30-45	...	...	...	...	... +... / -...	
Speakers aged 46 to 65	...	...	...	...	... +... / -...	<i>p</i> = ...
Speakers aged 66 or more	...	...	...	...	... +... / -...	
Language [Place] Item 2: ...	...	... (...%)	... (...%)	... (...%)	... +... / -... [83% CI: +... / -...]	
Female speakers	...	...	...	...	... +... / -... [83% CI: +... / -...]	<i>p</i> = ...
Male speakers	...	...	...	...	... +... / -... [83% CI: +... / -...]	
Younger speakers	...	...	...	...	... +... / -... [83% CI: +... / -...]	<i>p</i> = ...
Elder speakers	...	...	...	...	... +... / -... [83% CI: +... / -...]	
Speakers aged 18 to 29	...	...	...	...	... +... / -...	<i>p</i> = ...
Speakers aged 30-45	...	...	...	...	... +... / -...	
Speakers aged 46 to 65	...	...	...	...	... +... / -...	<i>p</i> = ...
Speakers aged 66 or more	...	...	...	...	... +... / -...	
Language [Place] Item 3: ...	...	... (...%)	... (...%)	... (...%)	... +... / -... [83% CI: +... / -...]	
Female speakers	...	...	...	...	... +... / -... [83% CI: +... / -...]	<i>p</i> = ...
Male speakers	...	...	...	...	... +... / -... [83% CI: +... / -...]	
Younger speakers	...	...	...	...	... +... / -... [83% CI: +... / -...]	<i>p</i> = ...
Elder speakers	...	...	...	...	... +... / -... [83% CI: +... / -...]	
Speakers aged 18 to 29	...	...	...	...	... +... / -...	<i>p</i> = ...
Speakers aged 30-45	...	...	...	...	... +... / -...	
Speakers aged 46 to 65	...	...	...	...	... +... / -...	<i>p</i> = ...
Speakers aged 66 or more	...	...	...	...	... +... / -...	

Table 2.2.4: Analysis: B.4. The adverbials’ situational attribution: When are they used?

Example for significance thresholds (if binary categories):

“No situation in particular” (1-5.4) || “In specific language domains” (5.5-10)

“No situation in particular” (1-5.4) || “In specialised language” (5.5-10)

B.3.b WHEN (other) On the basis of speaker judgment <i>Categorised under 1 and 10 are exclusive;</i> <i>Answers in absolute numbers</i>	0. Not sure (reported to 5,5)	1. <i>If appl. add cate go-ry</i>	5.5 No situation in particular / Both (add NS) <i>if appl.</i>	10. <i>If appl. add cate go-ry</i>	II.a Other situation attributions e.g., in specific language domains / specialised language (value) (scale 1-10)	II.b Significance of group dependency
Language [Place] Item 1: ...	...	... (...%)	<i>Report from above</i>	... (...%)	... +... / -... [83% CI: +... / -...]	
Female speakers	...	...	...	...	... +... / -... [83% CI: +... / -...]	<i>p</i> = ...
Male speakers	...	...	...	...	... +... / -... [83% CI: +... / -...]	
Younger speakers	...	...	<i>Idem</i>	...	... +... / -... [83% CI: +... / -...]	<i>p</i> = ...
Elder speakers	...	...	<i>Idem</i>	...	... +... / -... [83% CI: +... / -...]	
Speakers aged 18 to 29	...	...	...	...	... +... / -...	<i>p</i> = ...
Speakers aged 30-45	...	...	...	...	... +... / -...	
Speakers aged 46 to 65	...	...	...	...	... +... / -...	<i>p</i> = ...
Speakers aged 66 or more	...	...	...	...	... +... / -...	
Language [Place] Item 2: ...	...	... (...%)	<i>Idem</i>	... (...%)	... +... / -... [83% CI: +... / -...]	
Female speakers	...	...	...	...	... +... / -... [83% CI: +... / -...]	<i>p</i> = ...
Male speakers	...	...	...	...	... +... / -... [83% CI: +... / -...]	
Younger speakers	...	...	<i>Idem</i>	...	... +... / -... [83% CI: +... / -...]	<i>p</i> = ...
Elder speakers	...	...	<i>Idem</i>	...	... +... / -... [83% CI: +... / -...]	
Speakers aged 18 to 29	...	...	...	...	... +... / -...	<i>p</i> = ...
Speakers aged 30-45	...	...	...	...	... +... / -...	
Speakers aged 46 to 65	...	...	...	...	... +... / -...	<i>p</i> = ...
Speakers aged 66 or more	...	...	...	...	... +... / -...	
Language [Place] Item 3: ...	...	... (...%)	<i>Idem</i>	... (...%)	... +... / -... [83% CI: +... / -...]	
Female speakers	...	...	...	...	... +... / -... [83% CI: +... / -...]	<i>p</i> = ...
Male speakers	...	...	...	...	... +... / -... [83% CI: +... / -...]	
Younger speakers	...	...	<i>Idem</i>	...	... +... / -... [83% CI: +... / -...]	<i>p</i> = ...
Elder speakers	...	...	<i>Idem</i>	...	... +... / -... [83% CI: +... / -...]	
Speakers aged 18 to 29	...	...	...	...	... +... / -...	<i>p</i> = ...
Speakers aged 30-45	...	...	...	...	... +... / -...	
Speakers aged 46 to 65	...	...	...	...	... +... / -...	<i>p</i> = ...
Speakers aged 66 or more	...	...	...	...	... +... / -...	
Language [Place] Item 4: ...	...	... (...%)	<i>Idem</i>	... (...%)	... +... / -... [83% CI: +... / -...]	
Female speakers	...	...	...	...	... +... / -... [83% CI: +... / -...]	<i>p</i> = ...
Male speakers	...	...	...	...	... +... / -... [83% CI: +... / -...]	
Younger speakers	...	...	<i>Idem</i>	...	... +... / -... [83% CI: +... / -...]	<i>p</i> = ...
Elder speakers	...	...	<i>Idem</i>	...	... +... / -... [83% CI: +... / -...]	
Speakers aged 18 to 29	...	...	...	...	... +... / -...	<i>p</i> = ...
Speakers aged 30-45	...	...	...	...	... +... / -...	
Speakers aged 46 to 65	...	...	...	...	... +... / -...	<i>p</i> = ...
Speakers aged 66 or more	...	...	...	...	... +... / -...	

Table 2.2.4b: Analysis: B.4b. The adverbials' attribution to other situations: When else are they used?

2.2.5. How are the prepositional adverbials used?

Question B.4: Does this expression seem more written or spoken to you?

Possible answers: written/spoken/both.

Significance thresholds: “Written” (1-3.7) || “Both” (3.8-7.2) || “Spoken” (7.3-10)

B.4 HOW (code) On the basis of speaker judgment <i>Categories 1 and 10 are exclusive; Answers in absolute numbers</i>	0. No answer	NS reported to 5.5	1. Written	5.5 Both (add NS)	10. Spoken	II.a Perceptive code attributions (value) (scale 1-10)	II.b Significance of group dependency
Language [Place] Item 1: ...	...	...	... (...%)	... (...%)	... (...%)	... +... / -... [83% CI: +... / -...]	
Female speakers	...	...	...	...	...	... +... / -... [83% CI: +... / -...]	$p = \dots$
Male speakers	...	...	...	...	...	... +... / -... [83% CI: +... / -...]	
Younger speakers	...	...	...	...	...	... +... / -... [83% CI: +... / -...]	$p = \dots$
Elder speakers	...	...	...	...	...	... +... / -... [83% CI: +... / -...]	
Speakers aged 18 to 29	...	...	...	...	...	... +... / -...	$p = \dots$
Speakers aged 30-45	...	...	...	...	...	... +... / -...	
Speakers aged 46 to 65	...	...	...	...	...	... +... / -...	$p = \dots$
Speakers aged 66 or more	...	...	...	...	...	... +... / -...	
Language [Place] Item 2: ...	...	...	... (...%)	... (...%)	... (...%)	... +... / -... [83% CI: +... / -...]	
Female speakers	...	...	...	...	...	... +... / -... [83% CI: +... / -...]	$p = \dots$
Male speakers	...	...	...	...	...	... +... / -... [83% CI: +... / -...]	
Younger speakers	...	...	...	...	...	... +... / -... [83% CI: +... / -...]	$p = \dots$
Elder speakers	...	...	...	...	...	... +... / -... [83% CI: +... / -...]	
Speakers aged 18 to 29	...	...	...	...	...	... +... / -...	$p = \dots$
Speakers aged 30-45	...	...	...	...	...	... +... / -...	
Speakers aged 46 to 65	...	...	...	...	...	... +... / -...	$p = \dots$
Speakers aged 66 or more	...	...	...	...	...	... +... / -...	
Language [Place] Item 3: ...	...	...	... (...%)	... (...%)	... (...%)	... +... / -... [83% CI: +... / -...]	
Female speakers	...	...	...	...	...	... +... / -... [83% CI: +... / -...]	$p = \dots$
Male speakers	...	...	...	...	...	... +... / -... [83% CI: +... / -...]	
Younger speakers	...	...	...	...	...	... +... / -... [83% CI: +... / -...]	$p = \dots$
Elder speakers	...	...	...	...	...	... +... / -... [83% CI: +... / -...]	
Speakers aged 18 to 29	...	...	...	...	...	... +... / -...	$p = \dots$
Speakers aged 30-45	...	...	...	...	...	... +... / -...	
Speakers aged 46 to 65	...	...	...	...	...	... +... / -...	$p = \dots$
Speakers aged 66 or more	...	...	...	...	...	... +... / -...	
Language [Place] Item 4: ...	...	...	... (...%)	... (...%)	... (...%)	... +... / -... [83% CI: +... / -...]	
Female speakers	...	...	...	...	...	... +... / -... [83% CI: +... / -...]	$p = \dots$
Male speakers	...	...	...	...	...	... +... / -... [83% CI: +... / -...]	
Younger speakers	...	...	...	...	...	... +... / -... [83% CI: +... / -...]	$p = \dots$
Elder speakers	...	...	...	...	...	... +... / -... [83% CI: +... / -...]	
Speakers aged 18 to 29	...	...	...	...	...	... +... / -...	$p = \dots$
Speakers aged 30-45	...	...	...	...	...	... +... / -...	
Speakers aged 46 to 65	...	...	...	...	...	... +... / -...	$p = \dots$
Speakers aged 66 or more	...	...	...	...	...	... +... / -...	

Table 2.2.5: Analysis: B.4. The adverbials’ variation in terms of code: How are they used?

2.2.6. Do the adverbials present morphosyntactic prepositional variation?

Question C: Have you heard from any forms that are similar to this expression?
 Free answer. [If applicable]: Have you already heard XXX? Free answer.
 Thresholds: “Unknown” (under 2, according to the number of people answering)
 || “Little known” (up to 3.7) || “Well-known” (3.8-7.2) || “Very well-known” (7.3-10)

C.1 Prepositional variation without semantic change <i>Categories exclusive;</i> <i>Answers in absolute numbers / %</i>	0. Speakers do not know morpho-syntactic variation	10. Speakers mention they know morpho-syntactic variation (with the same meaning)	II. Value (scale 0-10)	Thresh old for un- known	III. Group dependency
Language [Place] Item 1: ...	... (... %)	... mentioned by ... speakers (... %)	... +... / -... [83% CI: +... / -...]		
Female speakers	... (... %)	... (... %)	... +... / -... [83% CI: +... / -...]		<i>p</i> =
Male speakers	... (... %)	... (... %)	... +... / -... [83% CI: +... / -...]		
Younger speakers	... (... %)	... (... %)	... +... / -... [83% CI: +... / -...]		<i>p</i> =
Elder speakers	... (... %)	... (... %)	... +... / -... [83% CI: +... / -...]		
Speakers aged 18 to 29	... (... %)	... (... %)	... +... / -... [83% CI: +... / -...]		<i>p</i> =
Speakers aged 30-45	... (... %)	... (... %)	... +... / -... [83% CI: +... / -...]		
Speakers aged 46 to 65	... (... %)	... (... %)	... +... / -... [83% CI: +... / -...]		<i>p</i> =
Speakers aged 66 or more	... (... %)	... (... %)	... +... / -... [83% CI: +... / -...]		
Language [Place] Item 2: ...	... (... %)	... mentioned by ... speakers (... %)	... +... / -... [83% CI: +... / -...]		
Female speakers	... (... %)	... (... %)	... +... / -... [83% CI: +... / -...]		<i>p</i> =
Male speakers	... (... %)	... (... %)	... +... / -... [83% CI: +... / -...]		
Younger speakers	... (... %)	... (... %)	... +... / -... [83% CI: +... / -...]		<i>p</i> =
Elder speakers	... (... %)	... (... %)	... +... / -... [83% CI: +... / -...]		
Speakers aged 18 to 29	... (... %)	... (... %)	... +... / -... [83% CI: +... / -...]		<i>p</i> =
Speakers aged 30-45	... (... %)	... (... %)	... +... / -... [83% CI: +... / -...]		
Speakers aged 46 to 65	... (... %)	... (... %)	... +... / -... [83% CI: +... / -...]		<i>p</i> =
Speakers aged 66 or more	... (... %)	... (... %)	... +... / -... [83% CI: +... / -...]		

Table 2.2.6.1: Analysis: C.1. The adverbials’ formal prepositional variation without semantic change

C.2 Prepositional variation with semantic change <i>Categories exclusive;</i> <i>Answers in absolute numbers / %</i>	0. Speakers do not know morpho-syntactic variation	10. Speakers mention they know morpho-syntactic variation with other meanings	II. Value (scale 0-10)	Threshold for unknown	III. Group dependency
Language [Place] Item 1: ...	... (... %)	... mentioned by ... speakers (... %)	... +... / -... [83% CI: +... / -...]		
Female speakers	... (... %)	...	... +... / -... [83% CI: +... / -...]		$p =$
Male speakers	... (... %)	...	... +... / -... [83% CI: +... / -...]		
Younger speakers	... (... %)	...	... +... / -... [83% CI: +... / -...]		$p =$
Elder speakers	... (... %)	...	... +... / -... [83% CI: +... / -...]		
Speakers aged 18 to 29	... (... %)	... (... %)	... +... / -...		$p =$
Speakers aged 30-45	... (... %)	... (... %)	... +... / -...		
Speakers aged 46 to 65	... (... %)	... (... %)	... +... / -...		$p =$
Speakers aged 66 or more	... (... %)	... (... %)	... +... / -...		
Language [Place] Item 2: ...	... (... %)	... mentioned by ... speakers (... %)	... +... / -... [83% CI: +... / -...]		
Female speakers	... (... %)	...	... +... / -... [83% CI: +... / -...]		$p =$
Male speakers	... (... %)	...	... +... / -... [83% CI: +... / -...]		
Younger speakers	... (... %)	...	... +... / -... [83% CI: +... / -...]		$p =$
Elder speakers	... (... %)	...	... +... / -... [83% CI: +... / -...]		
Speakers aged 18 to 29	... (... %)	... (... %)	... +... / -...		$p =$
Speakers aged 30-45	... (... %)	... (... %)	... +... / -...		
Speakers aged 46 to 65	... (... %)	... (... %)	... +... / -...		$p =$
Speakers aged 66 or more	... (... %)	... (... %)	... +... / -...		
Language [Place] Item 3: ...	... (... %)	... mentioned by ... speakers (... %)	... +... / -... [83% CI: +... / -...]		
Female speakers	... (... %)	...	... +... / -... [83% CI: +... / -...]		$p =$
Male speakers	... (... %)	...	... +... / -... [83% CI: +... / -...]		
Younger speakers	... (... %)	...	... +... / -... [83% CI: +... / -...]		$p =$
Elder speakers	... (... %)	...	... +... / -... [83% CI: +... / -...]		
Speakers aged 18 to 29	... (... %)	... (... %)	... +... / -...		$p =$
Speakers aged 30-45	... (... %)	... (... %)	... +... / -...		
Speakers aged 46 to 65	... (... %)	... (... %)	... +... / -...		$p =$
Speakers aged 66 or more	... (... %)	... (... %)	... +... / -...		

Table 2.2.6.2: Analysis: C.2. The adverbials' morphosyntactic (prepositional) variation with semantic change

2.2.7. Observations (questionnaire bloc D)

Free critical discussion.

3. Combining Data: Vitality

Significance thresholds:

“Unknown” (0) || “Vital –” (little vital) (>0 <2.5) || “Vital +” (2.5-7.5) || “Vital ++” (> 7.5)

A-B.1 Vitality <i>Categories non-exclusive Answers in median values</i>	Recognition (A.1): form ‘known’	Local recognition (A.2)	Perceptive frequency (B.1)	II. Vitality (median value) (scale 1-10)	III. Signi- ficance of group de- pendency
Weighting / combination	double- weighted	simple- weighted	simple- weighted	(2x A.1 + 1x A.2 + 1x B.1) : 5	
Language [Place] Item 1: ...	... +... / -...	... +... / -...	... +... / -...	... +... / -... [83% CI: +... / -...]	
Female speakers	... +... / -...	... +... / -...	... +... / -...	... +... / -... [83% CI: +... / -...]	<i>p</i> = ...
Male speakers	... +... / -...	... +... / -...	... +... / -...	... +... / -... [83% CI: +... / -...]	
Younger speakers	... +... / -...	... +... / -...	... +... / -...	... +... / -... [83% CI: +... / -...]	<i>p</i> = ...
Elder speakers	... +... / -...	... +... / -...	... +... / -...	... +... / -... [83% CI: +... / -...]	
Speakers aged 18 to 29	... +... / -...	... +... / -...	... +... / -...	... +... / -... [83% CI: +... / -...]	<i>p</i> = ...
Speakers aged 30-45	... +... / -...	... +... / -...	... +... / -...	... +... / -... [83% CI: +... / -...]	
Speakers aged 46 to 65	... +... / -...	... +... / -...	... +... / -...	... +... / -... [83% CI: +... / -...]	<i>p</i> = ...
Speakers aged 66 or more	... +... / -...	... +... / -...	... +... / -...	... +... / -... [83% CI: +... / -...]	
Language [Place] Item 2: ...	... +... / -...	... +... / -...	... +... / -...	... +... / -... [83% CI: +... / -...]	
Female speakers	... +... / -...	... +... / -...	... +... / -...	... +... / -... [83% CI: +... / -...]	<i>p</i> = ...
Male speakers	... +... / -...	... +... / -...	... +... / -...	... +... / -... [83% CI: +... / -...]	
Younger speakers	... +... / -...	... +... / -...	... +... / -...	... +... / -... [83% CI: +... / -...]	<i>p</i> = ...
Elder speakers	... +... / -...	... +... / -...	... +... / -...	... +... / -... [83% CI: +... / -...]	
Speakers aged 18 to 29	... +... / -...	... +... / -...	... +... / -...	... +... / -... [83% CI: +... / -...]	<i>p</i> = ...
Speakers aged 30-45	... +... / -...	... +... / -...	... +... / -...	... +... / -... [83% CI: +... / -...]	
Speakers aged 46 to 65	... +... / -...	... +... / -...	... +... / -...	... +... / -... [83% CI: +... / -...]	<i>p</i> = ...
Speakers aged 66 or more	... +... / -...	... +... / -...	... +... / -...	... +... / -... [83% CI: +... / -...]	

Table 3: Combining data. The adverbials’ vitality (based on A.1, A.2 and B.1)

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